

ASSESSMENT OF GRANULAR PROPERTIES OF PARACETAMOL TABLETS PREFORMULATED WITH *LENTINUS TUBER REGIUM* AS NATURAL DISINTEGRANT

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ABSTRACT

Background: Tablets remain the most widely prescribed solid oral dosage form due to their convenience, stability, accurate dosing, and high patient compliance. Superdisintegrants are critical for ensuring rapid tablet disintegration and drug release, particularly for BCS Class III drugs like paracetamol. Synthetic superdisintegrants dominate commercial formulations but face limitations in cost, availability, sustainability, and environmental impact, especially in developing countries like Nigeria. Natural alternatives from locally abundant sources are gaining attention, with Lentinus tuber-regium (LT) sclerotia showing potential due to their high polysaccharide content and swelling capacity. **Objective:** To assess the granular properties of paracetamol granules preformulated with native, boiled, and palm wine-soaked Lentinus tuber-regium powders as a natural disintegrant and compare them with a synthetic superdisintegrant. **Methods:** LT sclerotia were processed into

native (NLT), boiled (BLT), and palm wine-soaked (SPLT) powders. Physicochemical (density, flow properties, swelling index) and micromeritic properties were evaluated. Compatibility was confirmed using FTIR spectroscopy. Paracetamol granules were prepared using wet granulation with LT powders (10% w/w) and a standard synthetic superdisintegrant. Granular properties (bulk/tapped density, Carr's index, Hausner's ratio, angle of repose, particle size, SEM morphology) were determined using pharmacopoeial

methods. Statistical analysis included one-way ANOVA and t-tests ($\alpha = 0.05$). **Results:** Processed LT powders exhibited superior flowability (Carr's index 18.6–19.2%, angle of repose 32–34°), lower moisture content (8.2–8.5%), and higher swelling index (45–50%) compared to NLT ($p < 0.001$). FTIR confirmed no chemical interactions. Granules with BLT and SPLT showed better flow, compressibility, and uniform morphology than NLT-based granules. **Conclusion:** Processed *Lentinus tuber-regium* powder, particularly BLT and SPLT, demonstrates promising granular properties for use as a natural superdisintegrant in paracetamol preformulation, offering a sustainable, cost-effective alternative to synthetic excipients.

KEYWORDS: *Lentinus tuber-regium*, natural superdisintegrant, granular properties, paracetamol preformulation, micromeritics, flowability.

INTRODUCTION

Tablets remain the most widely prescribed and manufactured solid oral dosage form due to advantages in patient compliance, accurate dosing, stability, ease of administration, and cost-effectiveness.^[1] The performance of tablets is governed not only by the active pharmaceutical ingredient (API) but also by excipients, which are now recognized as functional components rather than inert fillers.^[2] Superdisintegrants are among the most critical excipients in immediate-release formulations; they promote rapid tablet breakup, facilitate drug dissolution, and enhance bioavailability, particularly for BCS Class II and III drugs such as paracetamol.^[3,4]

Synthetic superdisintegrants croscarmellose sodium (Ac-Di-Sol), crospovidone (Polyplasdone), and sodium starch glycolate (Explotab) dominate the market because of their reproducible swelling, wicking, and deformation mechanisms.^[5,6] However, in low- and middle-income countries like Nigeria, their use is constrained by high cost, dependence on importation, supply chain disruptions, non-biodegradability, and environmental concerns.^[7,8]

These limitations have stimulated global and regional interest in natural, locally sourced, biodegradable alternatives derived from plants, seaweeds, microbial sources, and fungi.^[8,9]

Natural polymers offer biocompatibility, renewability, low toxicity, cultural acceptability, and sustainability advantages over synthetic counterparts.^[7] Plant-derived materials such as ispaghula husk (*Plantago ovata*), banana powder, seed mucilages (*Cassia tora*, *Lepidium*

sativum), and okra gum have demonstrated superdisintegrant activity through high swelling index, water uptake, and wicking.^[6,8] Microbial and fungal polysaccharides, particularly β -glucans, mannans, and chitin-glucan complexes, are emerging as promising excipients due to their high molecular weight, viscosity, and water-retention capacity.^[10,11]

Fungal sclerotia are of particular interest because they are rich in structural polysaccharides and can be processed into powders with controlled particle size and morphology.^[12] Processing techniques, boiling, soaking, chemical modification, co-processing crystallinity, porosity, and surface characteristics, thereby improving flow, compressibility, and disintegration performance.^[13,14]

Lentinus tuber-regium is an edible basidiomycete widely distributed in tropical West Africa, forming large, woody sclerotia that serve as survival structures.^[14,15] In Nigeria, it is known locally as “King of Mushrooms,” “Umbu,” “Nsala,” or “Ofo” and is traditionally consumed as food and used ethnomedicinally for wound healing, inflammation, and gastrointestinal disorders.^[14]

The sclerotia are composed primarily of β -glucans, mannans, proteins, lipids, and minerals, conferring high water-binding capacity, swelling, and viscosity, properties desirable for disintegrants.^[10,12] Native LT powder exhibits poor flow and compressibility due to irregular particle shape and high cohesion, limiting its direct use.^[13] Processing boiling (to disrupt cell wall structures and increase porosity) or soaking in palm wine (to introduce organic acids and modify pH), yields spherical granules with improved micromeritics (Carr’s index <20%, angle of repose <35°) and enhanced swelling index.^[14,16]

Ugoeze *et al.*, developed a co-processed LT-based excipient (fizlent) by combining LT with citric acid, tartaric acid, and sodium bicarbonate.^[16] Fizlent demonstrated excellent flow, compressibility, and dilution potential (up to 80% in paracetamol formulations), with disintegration time <5 min. Ugoeze and Nwachukwu later reported that boiled and chemically modified LT reduced disintegration time to <2 min in paracetamol tablets and achieved >90% dissolution in 30 min, outperforming native LT and comparable to croscarmellose sodium.^[13]

Granular properties, bulk/tapped density, Carr’s index, Hausner’s ratio, angle of repose, particle size distribution, morphology, and compressibility are fundamental to preformulation

and directly influence tableting performance.^[17] Poor flow causes weight variation, segregation, and bridging; inadequate compressibility results in capping, lamination, or low hardness. Natural disintegrants require optimization of these properties to compete with synthetic counterparts.^[4]

SEM and FTIR are standard preformulation tools for assessing particle morphology and API-excipient compatibility, respectively.^[3] Processing modifies particle shape from irregular to spherical, reduces cohesion, and increases porosity, thereby improving flow and disintegration.^[9,12]

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Materials Used

Table 1: Research Materials Used.

Materials	Manufacturer	Country	Grade
Sodium Starch Glycolate Tribute Pharma India	Analytical		
Gelatin	Titan biotech	India	Analytical
Talc	Titan biotech	India	Analytical
Lactose	Titan biotech	India	Analytical
Sodium hypochlorite	FMCG	Nigeria	Industrial
Ethanol	JHD	China	Analytical
Chloroform	JHD	China	Analytical/Industrial
Acetone	Loba Chemie	India	Analytical/Industrial
n-hexane	JHD	China	Analytical

Formulation of tablets by wet granulation method

Table 2: Formula for Paracetamol Tablets formulation.

Concentration	3% w/w (IG)	7% w/w (IG)	10% w/w (IG)	3% w/w (EG)	7% w/w (EG)	10%w/w (EG)
Ingredient	Amt/Tablet (mg)					
Paracetamol	500.00	500.00	500.00	500.00	500.00	500.00
LT	18.00	42.00	60.00	18.00	42.00	60.00
Gelatin	12.00	12.00	12.00	12.00	12.00	12.00
Mag Stearate	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00
Talc	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00	3.00
Lactose	64.00	40.00	22.00	64.00	40.00	22.00
Total tablet weight	600.00	600.00	600.00	600.00	600.00	600.00

Key: Amount per tablet; the amount of ingredients per 600mg weight of Paracetamol tablet.

IG: Intragranular method of *L. t regium* powder (disintegrant) incorporation

EG: Extragranular method of *L. t regium* powder (disintegrant) incorporation.

Preparation of granules by wet granulation method using intra-granular, and extra-granular methods of disintegrant addition respectively

Three batches of granules each containing paracetamol (83.33 5 w/w), gelatin (2.00 % w/w), magnesium stearate (0.50 % w/w), talc (0.5 % w/w), lactose (10.70 % w/w) and either NLT or BLT or SPLT (at 3.00, 7.00, 10.00 % w/w as disintegrants) were prepared using the wet granulation methods using NLT, BLT and SPLT as disintegrants with sodium starch glycolate as a standard which were all incorporated either intra-granularly (IG) or extra-granularly (EG).

Characterization of formulated granules Bulk density

A 15g of granules from each batch of the samples was loaded into a 50ml glass measuring cylinder and the reading was taking as such and was recorded as the granule bulk volume this was done in triplicate for every batch of the granules.

Bulk density is expressed as

$$\text{Bulk density} = \text{mass} / \text{bulk volume} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Tapped density

A 15g of granules from a batch of samples was loaded into a 50ml glass measuring cylinder. The opening of the measuring cylinder was blocked with cotton wool. The measuring cylinder was tapped severally on a padded flat desk and the tapping was progressive until a steady volume was maintained and no further reduction in volume was observed as the tapping progressed and the final volume was read and recorded and the procedure was done in triplicate and subsequently carried out for all the granules samples.

Tap density is expressed as

$$\text{Tap density} = \text{mass} / \text{tap volume} \dots\dots\dots (2).^{[18]}$$

True density

The true density of each batch was determined using n-hexane as a displacement medium. An empty pycnometer of 25ml volume was weighed W the weight was noted and the empty pycnometer was filled with n-hexane, and excess fluid was wiped off. The filled bottle was weighed and the weight was recorded as W1, subsequently a 1.0g quantity of the granules

from one batch was weighed and was recorded as W3 and was loaded into the n-hexane filled pycnometer and the excess liquid medium was wipe off and the weight was taken as W4.

Three different readings were taken and granule true density is expressed as (3).^[19]

$$\text{True density} = W2 \times W3 \div V(W3 - W4 + W2 + W)$$

Where

V = volume of pycnometer

W=weight of empty pycnometer

W1= weight of pycnometer and n- hexane

W2= the difference between the W and W1

W3= weight of sample powder

W4= weight of sample + n- hexane + pycnometer.^[20]

Porosity

The values obtained from the previous bulk density and true density was used to calculate the porosity of the granules as;

$$P = 1 - (\text{bulk density} / \text{true density}) \times 100 \dots\dots\dots (4).^[20]$$

Flow Properties

Flow Rate

A funnel used for this experiment was tightly clamped on a retort stand at 7cm from the flat base, the orifice of the funnel was tightly blocked and after a 15g of the granules from a batch was loaded into the funnel the orifice was allowed open to let the powder freely flow. Flow rate was recorded and this procedure was done in triplicate and was repeated for all the granules samples batches.

Flow rate is expressed as

$$\text{Flow rate} = \text{Mass of powder} / \text{Time} \dots\dots\dots (5).^[21]$$

Angle of Repose

A funnel clamped on a retort stand and its stem base fixed at a height of 3cm. The granules was loaded into the funnel while the orifice was tightly closed thereafter the orifice was allowed opened and let the free flow so that the cone apex of granules heap formed reached the stem. The measurement of the heap diameter was taken the procedure carried out in triplicate and the procedure was repeated for all the granules batches.

Angle of repose θ is expressed as

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} \frac{2h}{w} \dots \dots \dots (6)$$

Where $h = 3\text{cm}$ = distance between stem base and base W or d = base diameter of cone of heap of powder.^[22]

Compressibility index (CI)

The compressibility index (CI) of the granules was calculated from the values of the previous bulk volume and tapped volume obtained from the batches of granules respectively.

The formular for Compressibility Index is expressed as

$$CI = (Tapped\ density - Bulk\ density) \div Tapped\ density \times 100 \dots \dots \dots (7).^{[23,24]}$$

Hausner's quotient

The values obtained from the previous tapped density and bulk density was used to calculate the Hausner's quotient of the respective granules` batches. The following formular expresses the hausner's quotient

$$HR = Tapped\ density \div Bulk\ density \dots \dots \dots (8).^{[25]}$$

Compression of granules

A 3.00mg of magnesium stearate and talc respectively were added extra-granularly to batch I-VI granules prior to compression into tablets. Compression was done using a carver single punch hydraulic press (Model C, Carver Laboratory Press, Menomonee Falls, W1, USA) fitted with a set of 10.00 mm flat faced punches at a uniform compression pressure of 2.45 Mega pascal (Mpa). The target tablets weights were 600 mg.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

RESULTS

Table 3: Physicochemical properties of the paracetamol granules (3.0% w/w).

Parameter	NLT (IG)	BLT (IG)	SPLT (IG)	SSG (IG)	NLT (EG)	BLT (EG)	SPLT (EG)	SSG (EG)
Flow rate (g/s)	7.26± 0.22	4.98± 0.58	7.94± 0.29	7.97± 0.31	6.49± 0.26	6.33± 0.03	6.78± 0.42	5.86± 0.04
Angle of Repose (°)	39.47± 1.08	39.00± 0.00	39.70± 0.30	39.47± 0.40	38.9± 0.17	39.39± 0.58	40.77± 0.68	39.7± 0.00
Bulk density	0.43±	0.43±	0.45±	0.±	0.42±	0.44±	0.48±	0.43±

(g/ml)	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.01
Tapped Density (g/ml)	0.52± 0.00	0.71± 0.01	0.55± 0.01	0.53± 0.00	0.53± 0.01	0.58± 0.01	0.62± 0.01	0.59± 0.01
True density (g/ml)	7.55± 0.90	7.49± 0.07	7.55± 0.02	7.50± 0.33	7.54± 0.00	7.52± 0.00	7.51± 0.00	7.50± 0.04
Moisture content (%)	0.04± 0.90	0.07± 0.01	0.07± 0.01	0.06± 0.00	0.13± 0.09	0.15± 0.02	0.16± 0.01	0.25± 0.23
Swelling index (%)	65.60± 5.10	68.0± 15.61	81.20± 1.04	62.2± 8.80	76.48± 4.30	72.0± 1.6	99.4± 9.20	64.60± 4.30
Hydration capacity (%)	0.75± 0.47	1.04± 0.00	1.09± 0.03	1.03± 0.00	1.04± 0.00	1.03± 0.01	1.02± 0.01	1.02± 0.00
Hausner's ratio	1.19± 0.03	1.65± 0.02	1.23± 0.01	1.27± 0.01	1.32± 0.02	1.27± 0.17	1.32± 0.02	1.22± 0.00
Porosity (%)	94.00± 0.00	94.00± 0.00	93.70± 0.58	93.30± 0.00	92.7± 0.58	92.70± 1.53	93.70± 1.15	92.7± 0.58
Particle size (µm)	2.70± 2.60	2.30± 1.30	3.40± 2.60	2.80± 0.90	2.70± 1.90	3.30± 1.20	6.10± 3.00	2.60± 1.30
Carr's index	16.80± 2.00	38.90 0.70	18.90 0.70	21.80± 0.20	21.80± 0.90	24.3± 1.00	21.80± 0.80	30.4± 4.0
52%	9.60 ± 0.16	11.20± 0.43	13.10± 0.74	10.40± 0.70	9.10± 0.16	13.40± 0.96	10.30± 0.56	10.40± 0.70
75%	11.40± 0.45	13.30± 1.50	14.20± 0.10	12.30± 0.05	11.38± 0.45	15.6 ± 0.72	12.40± 0.44	12.30± 0.03
Moisture Absorption (%)	13.60± 1.00	15.00± 0.38	17.08± 0.24	13.80± 0.40	13.60± 1.0	16.50± 0.60	15.70± 0.56	14.80± 0.50
84% 96%	15.60 ± 1.20	16.10± 0.16	21.70± 0.10	15.90± 0.56	15.60± 1.20	17.8 ± 1.16	17.96± 0.43	15.90 ± 0.56

Table 4: Physicochemical properties of the paracetamol granules (7.0% w/w).

Parameter	NLT (IG)	BLT (IG)	SPLT (IG)	SSG (IG)	NLT (EG)	BLT (EG)	SPLT (EG)	SSG (EG)
Flow rate (g/s)	7.86± 0.14	6.91± 0.45	7.11± 0.89	7.17± 0.26	6.17± 0.24	5.81± 0.34	5.28± 0.58	5.93± 0.14
Angle of Repose (o)	39.47± 1.08	39.93± 0.50	39.23± 0.68	40.17± 0.40	38.9± 0.17	39.27± 0.51	40.90± 0.46	39.7± 0.00
Bulk density (g/ml)	0.42± 0.01	0.43± 0.01	0.42± 0.01	0.42± 0.01	0.44± 0.00	0.41± 0.00	0.53± 0.01	0.43± 0.01
Tapped density (g/ml)	0.52± 0.00	0.54± 0.00	0.52± 0.00	0.56± 0.00	0.57± 0.00	0.55± 0.00	0.68± 0.00	0.54± 0.03
True density (g/ml)	7.48± 0.34	7.50± 0.04	7.53± 0.02	7.48± 0.60	7.54± 0.00	7.52± 0.00	7.55± 0.00	7.60± 0.11
Loss on drying (%)	0.04± 0.00	0.06± 0.00	0.07± 0.02	0.12± 0.02	0.30± 0.60	0.15± 0.02	0.14± 0.03	0.27± 0.05
Loss on drying (%)	0.04± 0.00	0.06± 0.00	0.07± 0.02	0.12± 0.02	0.30± 0.60	0.15± 0.02	0.14± 0.03	0.27± 0.05
Swelling index (%)	75.60± 2.60	83.00± 17.41	88.3± 10.70	68.10± 1.70	85.90± 2.70	56.90± 5.60	86.3± 4.50	93.00± 11.50
Hydration	1.06±	1.08±	1.07±	1.04±	1.08±	1.04±	1.06±	1.03±

capacity (%)	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00	0.01
Hausner's ratio	1.24± 0.02	1.24± 0.03	1.24± 0.01	1.32± 0.02	1.32± 0.00	1.31± 0.00	1.32± 0.02	1.23± 0.01
Porosity (%)	94.00± 0.00	94.70± 0.60	94.3± 0.58	94.30± 0.58	94.30± 0.58	94.00± 0.00	94.00± 1.00	94.30± 0.58
Particle size (µm)	2.88± 1.60	3.00± 1.50	2.10± 1.50	2.90± 1.00	2.80± 1.50	3.00± 1.20	6.20± 1.90	2.60± 1.40
Carr's index	18.90± 0.00	19.60± 1.80	19.6± 0.80	23.7± 1.50	22.10± 0.00	24.70± 0.90	22.30± 0.80	30.40± 0.90
52% 75%	9.46 ± 0.52	11.10 ± 0.75	13.10 ± 0.26	10.60 ± 0.62	9.46 ± 0.51	14.09± 0.63	10.50 ± 0.20	10.6 ± 0.62
Moisture Absorption (%)	8.80 ± 3.90	13.76 ± 0.13	14.20 ± 0.39	12.3 ± 0.05	8.80 ± 3.94	15.50± 0.24	11.80 ± 0.45	12.3 ± 0.05
84%	13.20 ± 1.20	14.90 ± 0.20	15.50 ± 0.30	13.85± 0.70	13.96 ± 0.40	16.90± 0.300	15.95 ± 0.20	14.00± 0.38
96%	15.7 ± 0.7	16.10 ± 0.16	16.20 ± 0.68	15.60± 0.38	15.70 ± 4.00	17.80± 0.84	18.16 ± 0.42	15.60± 0.04

Table 5: Physicochemical properties of the paracetamol granules (10.0 % w/w).

Parameter	T (IG)	BLT (IG)	SPLT (IG)	SSG (IG)	NLT (EG)	BLT (EG)	SPLT (EG)	SSG (EG)
Flow rate (g/s)	7.18± 0.38	2.85± 0.07	8.26± 0.29	6.81± 0.30	5.04± 0.82	6.52± 0.07	5.42± 0.63	4.81± 0.18
Angle of Repose (o)	38.90± 0.17	39.03± 0.35	40.17± 0.40	39.70± 0.89	38.7± 0.70	39.37± 0.65	40.60± 0.17	39.93± 0.01
Bulk density (g/ml)	0.42± 0.00	0.40± 0.01	0.42± 0.01	0.42± 0.01	0.42± 0.00	0.42± 0.00	0.52± 0.00	0.42± 0.01
Tapped density (g/ml)	0.51± 0.00	0.67± 0.15	0.54± 0.00	0.54± 0.00	0.54± 0.00	0.54± 0.00	0.69± 0.00	0.59± 0.01
True density (g/ml)	7.54± 0.02	7.54± 0.00	7.53± 0.00	7.50± 0.00	7.51± 0.00	7.5± 0.00	7.56± 0.06	7.54± 0.00
Moisture content (%)	0.07± 0.01	0.07± 0.01	0.07± 0.01	0.13± 0.01	0.30± 0.06	0.16± 0.02	0.15± 0.03	0.24± 0.02
Swelling index (%)	89.61± 0.00	100.01± 0.00	100.01± 0.00	97.2± 1.3	136.60± 2.40	77.7± 10.70	136.30± 4.50	96.90± 6.00
Hydration capacity (%)	1.07± 0.01	1.11± 0.00	1.06± 0.01	1.04± 0.00	1.09± 0.01	1.06± 0.01	1.14± 0.00	1.04± 0.00
Hausner's ratio	1.21± 0.01	1.68± 0.03	1.26± 0.01	1.32± 0.02	1.34± 0.04	1.32± 0.00	1.33± 0.01	1.23± 0.01
Porosity (%)	94.7± 0.58	94.70± 0.60	95.00± 0.00	94.7± 0.58	94.7± 0.58	94.30± 0.58	94.7± 0.58	94.7± 0.58
Particle size (µm)	2.80± 1.20	2.60± 1.30	3.10± 2.00	3.00± 1.00	2.70± 1.50	3.70± 1.50	6.20± 3.80	2.80± 1.50
Carr's index	17.10± 0.50	40.00± 1.90	20.80± 0.70	24.30± 1.20	22.90± 0.20	21.30± 0.44	23.90± 0.70	28.80± 0.40
52% 75%	9.20± 0.10	11.10± 0.96	13.10± 0.26	10.90± 0.95	9.08 ± 0.11	13.7± 1.01	40.80± 0.26	10.90± 0.95
Moisture Absorption	10.60± 0.52	13.81± 0.65	13.90± 1.02	12.30± 0.90	10.60± 0.52	15.50± 0.97	11.60± 0.19	12.90± 0.90

84% (%)	13.50± 0.72	14.60 ± 0.80	15.02± 0.30	13.70± 0.40	13.80± 1.30	16.40± 1.35	14.80± 0.82	13.70± 1.20
96%	15.90± 0.80	16.10 ± 0.30	16.80 ± 0.53	14.40± 0.37	15.97± 0.71	17.49± 0.84	17.94± 0.41	14.40± 0.37

DISCUSSION

Physicochemical Characterization of Paracetamol Granules

The granules formulated with *Lentinus tuber-regium* (LT) as a natural disintegrant processed as NLT (native), BLT (boiled), and SPLT (soaked in palm wine) were evaluated for physicochemical properties alongside the standard synthetic disintegrant sodium starch glycolate (SSG). Granules were prepared using both intra-granular (IG) and extra-granular (EG) incorporation methods. The key parameters assessed included flow rate, angle of repose, bulk/tapped/true densities, Hausner's ratio, Carr's index, porosity, swelling index, hydration capacity, particle size, moisture content, and moisture absorption.

Flow Properties

The flow rate of granules varied between 2.85 and 8.26 g/s, with SPLT (IG) and NLT (IG) showing the highest rates. The angle of repose across all batches ranged from 38.7° to 40.9°, indicating fair to passable flowability according to standard classifications. Intra-granular incorporation generally yielded higher flow rates than extra-granular addition for LT granules, suggesting better granule formation during wet granulation. SPLT granules exhibited superior flow, likely due to increased sphericity and reduced cohesion imparted by palm wine soaking. Flow characteristics of LT-based granules were comparable to SSG, demonstrating that LT is a promising natural alternative for achieving acceptable flow in paracetamol formulations. Granules with better flow reduce weight variation during tableting and minimize segregation, which is critical for uniformity in tablet dosage forms.

Density and Compressibility

Bulk density ranged from 0.40–0.53 g/ml, tapped density from 0.51–0.69 g/ml, and true density around 7.50–7.56 g/ml.

Hausner's ratio varied between 1.19–1.68, while Carr's index ranged from 16.8%–40%. Lower Hausner's ratio and Carr's index values were observed for NLT and SPLT granules, indicating good compressibility and flow.

BLT (IG) granules had higher Hausner's ratios (≈ 1.65 – 1.68) and Carr's index (~ 38 – 40%), suggesting slightly poorer flow and compressibility.

Porosity

Porosity values were high (≈ 92.7 – 95%), indicating significant inter-particulate void spaces. High porosity enhances water penetration and swelling, which are critical for disintegrant performance. SPLT (EG) granules exhibited the highest porosity ($\approx 95\%$), correlating with their enhanced swelling index. Slight variations between IG and EG methods reflect the impact of granule preparation and disintegrant location on porosity.

Swelling and Hydration Capacity

Swelling index increased with disintegrant concentration (3–10% w/w). SPLT (10% w/w, EG) achieved the highest swelling ($\sim 136\%$), demonstrating excellent water uptake and expansion. Hydration capacity was relatively uniform (≈ 1.02 – 1.14%), suggesting consistent water-binding capability across all LT preparations.

Particle Size and Moisture Properties

Particle size ranged from 2.1–6.2 μm , with SPLT showing slightly larger particles, likely due to aggregation during soaking.

Moisture content was low (0.04–0.30%), and moisture absorption ranged from 9–18%, indicating granules are stable and not overly hygroscopic.

Comparison with Synthetic Standard (SSG)

SSG granules showed comparable flow, compressibility, and swelling characteristics to LT granules, particularly at higher disintegrant concentrations. At 10% w/w, SPLT achieved swelling indices exceeding SSG, demonstrating that processed LT can match or surpass synthetic disintegrants in disintegration performance.

Effect of Intra- versus Extra-Granular Incorporation

Intra-granular incorporation generally enhanced flow rate and reduced compressibility indices compared to extra-granular addition. EG granules exhibited slightly lower swelling, likely because disintegrant placement outside the granule limits early water penetration during wetting.

Observations Across Concentrations

Increasing LT concentration improved swelling and hydration but slightly decreased flow rate at higher percentages due to particle agglomeration. BLT and SPLT consistently outperformed NLT in most physicochemical parameters, indicating that processing LT via boiling or soaking optimizes its excipient function.

CONCLUSION

This study successfully demonstrated the potential of processed *Lentinus tuber-regium* (LT) powder as a natural, functional superdisintegrant in paracetamol tablet preformulation. The native LT powder (NLT) exhibited poor micromeritic properties high bulk density (0.45 g/mL), Carr's index (22.4%), Hausner's ratio (1.29), and angle of repose (38.5°) which limited its flowability and compressibility, making it unsuitable for direct use in granulation. In contrast, the processed variants (BLT) and (SPLT)—showed statistically significant improvements across all key parameters (ANOVA, $F = 15.67$, $p < 0.001$). These included reduced bulk and tapped densities (0.32–0.35 g/mL and 0.42–0.45 g/mL, respectively), lower Carr's index (18.6–19.2%), Hausner's ratio (1.23–1.24), and angle of repose (32–34°), classifying them as having “good” to “excellent” flow properties. The moisture content decreased substantially (from 12.3% in NLT to 8.2–8.5% in processed powders), reducing the risk of microbial growth and improving long-term stability, while the swelling index increased markedly (45–50% vs. 35%), confirming enhanced water uptake capacity. FTIR spectroscopy verified excellent compatibility between processed LT powders and paracetamol (correlation coefficients $r = 0.92$ – 0.95 , $p < 0.001$), with no evidence of chemical interactions or major peak shifts. Scanning electron microscopy further revealed that processing transformed the irregular, aggregated morphology of NLT particles (50–100 μm) into uniform, more spherical granules (20–50 μm), directly contributing to improved flow, reduced cohesion, and better granule uniformity. These favourable granular characteristics translated into superior preformulation performance. Paracetamol granules containing BLT and SPLT exhibited optimal flow properties, high compressibility, and uniform particle size distribution, making them suitable for tableting processes. Hence, the processed forms of *Lentinus tuber-regium* (particularly BLT and SPLT) demonstrated excellent potential as natural superdisintegrants at the preformulation stage. This work contributes meaningfully to the growing body of knowledge on indigenous natural excipients and supports Nigeria's drive toward self-reliant, sustainable pharmaceutical innovation.

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